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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AND
ASSOCIATED COMORBIDITIES IN ALLIED HOSPITAL
FAISALABAD, PAKISTAN**

Dr. Zuby Tufail, Dr. Sadia Sultan, Dr. Mehwish Fayyaz

Abstract:

Objective: To determine prevalence and associated comorbidities of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) among patients visiting rheumatology department of Allied hospital Faisalabad, Pakistan. **Methodology:** A retrospective study was conducted at the Rheumatology department of Allied Hospital Faisalabad, Pakistan. Total 1200 medical records were reviewed. Patients of 16 years old and above of both gender were included in study. Data was analyzed by SPSS. **Results:** Among 1200 patients with rheumatic symptoms, 543(45.2%) patients were diagnosed cases of RA. Prevalence rate was higher among females 412(77.5%) , mostly fall in 31-45years age group as compared to males 131(24.1%). Hypertension 124 (22.8%), diabetes mellitus 211 (38.8%) and ischemic heart disease 89 (16.39%) were majorly reported comorbidities associated with rheumatoid arthritis.

Corresponding author:

Zuby Tufail

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INTRODUCTION:

Rheumatoid arthritis is a multifaceted disease which produces articular symptoms and damage, leading to disability. It is characterized by persistent synovial inflammation, bones erosion and articular destruction. Many epidemiological studies have been conducted to estimate the prevalence of the disease. It affects 0.5-1% of population all over the world[1].

Prevalence rate of RA in developing countries is variable. Reported Studies revealed lower prevalence rate in Nigeria,[2] Indonesia[3] and Africa[4] than that reported from the western countries.

A reported study in southern Pakistan, Karachi, revealed prevalence of RA is 0.142%,[5] while in northern Pakistan the estimated prevalence is 0.55%[6].

The objective of current study was to estimate prevalence and associated comorbidities of RA among patients of Allied hospital Faisalabad, Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY:

A retrospective study, conducted at the Rheumatology department of Allied Hospital Faisalabad, Pakistan, from January 2019 to June 2019. A total of 1200 medical records were reviewed. Diagnosed cases of rheumatoid arthritis, of both gender were included in our study. Patients of 16 years old and above were included. All patients were examined by experienced rheumatologists and satisfied the 1987 modified ACR classification principles of RA. Prevalence rate of RA and associated comorbidities were identified through rheumatology case records. Data was analyzed by SPSS.

RESULT:

Among 1200 patients with rheumatic symptoms, 543(45.2%) patients were diagnosed cases of RA. Out of 543 patients, 412(77.5%) were females and 131(24.1%) were males. Out of these 25 males and 78 females belongs to age group between 16-30 years, while 63 males and 233 females being between the ages of 31-45 years. Whereas 43 males and 101 females belonged to 46-60 years of age group as presented by Figure1.

Figure 1. Patient's distribution among different age groups

RA factor was found to be positive in 71.4% patients. Out of 412 females and 131 males with RA, 73.2% and 81% were seropositive respectively. Reported comorbidities associated with RA were hypertension 12.6%, diabetes mellitus 18.7%, ischemic heart disease 15.6% and others documented in table 1.

Table 1. Comorbidities in Rheumatoid arthritis patient

Comorbidities	Frequency (%age)
Hypertension	124 (22.8%)
Diabetes mellitus	211 (38.8%)
Ischemic heart disease	89 (16.39%)
Tuberculosis	63 (11.6%)
Asthma	44 (8.10%)
Hyperthyroidism	5 (0.9%)
Hypothyroidism	7 (1.2%)

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded from the study that prevalence rate of RA dominates among females as compared to males. Prevalence rate of RA was higher among the age group of 31-45 years. Hypertension, diabetes mellitus and ischemic heart disease were majorly reported comorbidities associated with rheumatoid arthritis.

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